

METHODS OF WORKING WITH FREE ASSIMILATING STUDENTS IN CLASS

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the process of educating students, increasing the activity of students with poor academic performance in the process of transferring knowledge, data in textbooks, ensuring the catch-up of their peers, the formation of knowledge, skills, qualifications and competencies, the problems that arise in the acquisition of knowledge and the methods used to solve them. , as well as issues such as good results achieved through this will be disclosed.

The most important elements of modern education have been formed since ancient times. Educational purpose, content, form, method and means are traditional categories used to analyze the content of educational processes. It is these categories that appear as the subject of the activity of the pedagogue who organizes the educational process in a certain subject, specialty or specialization. It acts as a systematizing factor of the legitimacy and criteria of pedagogically oriented pedagogical activity. A modern teacher should understand that he should not be an "actor" in the course of the lesson, but rather a "director". For this, he needs to be familiar with several new educational methods. Here, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev stated in his speeches that it is necessary to form and educate patriotic individuals who can think independently and do the right and acceptable work.

In fact, we cannot create a foundation for young people to become highly qualified specialists without enjoying the achievements of modern science and technology, science in general. First of all, it is important to provide students with correct and appropriate knowledge in the process of primary education. Based on the observations, we can say that during the period of primary education, reading activities take the place of playing activities. Studying becomes a child's duty and social duty. In the process of studying, he learns the skills of keeping his textbooks and school supplies in order, getting up on time, going to school on time, and completing homework assignments. The student becomes more and more responsible. Knowledge increases the child's level, ensures mental development, affects the growth of intuition and will. However, even during this period, the child's attention is still unstable. In primary school, changes occur in the student's memory. Starting from the first

grade, the student voluntarily remembers most of the educational material during the educational process. At the same time, he should always control himself. As a result, the student's memory improves and his thinking grows. 7-8-year-old children still think concretely. They only think about what they perceive or imagine. The first manifestations of logical thinking begin to form. In the third and fourth grades, students learn some concepts of scientific knowledge. During this period, emotional experiences occur in the psyche of students.

Students become interested in a subject or lesson. They realize that education is a duty. A high assessment of the student's work during the lesson gives rise to emotional experiences such as mental refreshment, joy, and pride in the students. However, there are also cases where students are lagging behind in subjects and their mastery is low. It is necessary for each elementary school teacher to conduct individual work with these students and identify their shortcomings in time and find a solution to it as much as possible. Therefore, a teacher of primary education must be mature in all aspects, a sharp diplomat, a master of his profession, a person with intellectual potential.

In the process of teaching in every class, we encounter students with poor mastery of subjects. Working with these students requires high qualifications from the teacher. In this process, the teacher should use new methods, increase the activity of low-learning students, and thereby ensure that low-learning students catch up with their peers. Only then is it considered that each primary school teacher was able to properly manage his activities and implement the process of individual work with each student. Teaching independent learners to work independently is effective. Independent activity makes a person alert and responsive. This activity should be developed in harmony with the education of young schoolchildren. For this, first of all, it is necessary to mentally prepare students for independent activities, to instill confidence in them that they can do something and do it well.

Types of independent work, first of all, should be carefully thought out by the teacher, oriented to the educational goal and continuous. In this, the opportunity of each student should be taken into account, age characteristics, interests should not be neglected. One of the conditions for the mental development of students is to complete tasks by "remembering". In this case, special attention is paid to the ability to define the plan and choose the work method while understanding (imagining) the purpose of the work to be performed, to be able to independently find the mistakes made and to correct them. It is useful to choose convenient methods, ask guiding questions, and recommend key words so that students can complete tasks quickly and correctly.

The instinct of imitation plays a big role in the formation of character in children. The study of the factors that cause free learning in the process of primary education, the psychological characteristics of students who do not learn, makes it possible to develop a system of measures and activities aimed at preventing the student's lack of learning during the educational process. will give. the system of activities for the prevention of free learning allows each student to comprehensively develop all the main components of real learning opportunities, i.e. to simultaneously develop the intellectual, willful, emotional spheres of a person, his education and upbringing should be aimed at providing, developing a positive

attitude to study and to the team, forming his ability to work. Underestimating the importance of the formation of one of the real educational opportunities for the student has a negative impact on the integrity of the system. As a result, it does not lead to successful prevention of idle appropriation.

It is important to protect students from stress and various psychological effects, to strengthen their knowledge through interesting games. The teacher's use of games that encourage students to be smart and quick and to express their thoughts correctly and clearly gives effective results. For example, in the game "Find the missing one", various geometric shapes are randomly placed on the blackboard or magnetic board. When the students finish looking at the shapes, the teacher says "Night". The children closed their eyes. The teacher takes some of the shapes, hides them and says "Day". Pupils should open their eyes and say which shapes have disappeared.

Identifying and working with slow learning students requires special perseverance and responsibility from the teacher. Therefore, in order to deal with this category of children, first of all, it is necessary to conduct a one-on-one conversation and determine their interests. Methods such as keeping a special journal, regularly monitoring children's learning, keeping a book of special activities for students in the subject they are struggling with are also effective. It is also important to encourage positive changes in students. To increase the activity of idle learners, it is necessary to develop their ability to think independently and speak. Various fairy tales can be used for this.

A teacher should use many other methods in teaching. The most important thing is that they work. It is also important to organize reading classes for students with low mastery. Through this, not only the reading literacy of the student increases, but also his worldview expands. There are many stories, especially in primary school textbooks.

The use of different types of educational tasks is up to the student. helps to approach creatively and apply theoretical knowledge in practice. To achieve this, it is necessary to strengthen and improve the knowledge of students on the basis of materials different from those that formed their initial understanding, imagination and skills. Also, it is desirable that these materials consist of multiple-choice tasks, and each of them should be a logical task related to specific knowledge. The placement of learning exercises in this way helps to create new connections in the minds of students and, accordingly, to better master the material.

The use of state advanced educational technologies by low-achieving students is an important issue. Because that student could not accept education in traditional classes or in classes that are always conducted as a team. Therefore, it is necessary to use all methods individually with students with low learning ability, and then to involve them in collective methods and the process of education as always.

In conclusion, the use of technologies in modern education is of great importance in organizing the process of working with low-assimilation students. Therefore, new methods, as well as the use of science, integrally connect educational technologies with this process. I think we should go. In this way, we will have the right approach to pedagogical activity and increase the efficiency of working with students, and we will achieve the formation of passive students' knowledge, skills, qualifications and competences.

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